

Embodied emissions

‘Embodied emissions’ or ‘Embodied Carbon’ is the amount of carbon pollution emitted during the manufacture, gathering of raw materials, transportation and disposal of a device.

When evaluating the carbon footprint of a piece of DRI equipment, embodied emissions can make up a substantial part of the total emissions.

- We cannot reach Net Zero without addressing embodied carbon!

Material extraction
and manufacture

Transportation and
installation

Use, maintenance,
operational energy and water

Decommissioning
and disposal

Production and transportation

Active carbon during use

Disposal

Full life cycle

The challenges of embodied emissions

desktop machines, laptops, local servers and small clusters contributions to UKRI emissions are of the same order as the UKRI-managed facilities

Embodied carbon costs of compute equipment are **hard to obtain** and often **generic in nature**

- There are aspects of embodied emissions that are not under direct control of UKRI
- Accounting correctly for embodied emissions without double-counting with supplier emissions
- Embodied carbon increasingly makes up a higher proportion of total carbon as equipment becomes more efficient

There are actions we can take to both maximise the use of embedded carbon within the current UKRI DRI and expand sustainably to minimise embodied emissions.

What we can do

Making the most of embodied carbon

- Extending equipment lifetime or donating old equipment
- Maximising utilisation of DRI resources

DRI upgrade considerations

- Optimising use of current DRI reduces need for expansion
- Does increased efficiency of new equipment make up for additional embodied carbon?
- Avoid 'rebound effect' – upgrading equipment should lead to carbon savings not just increased capacity

Procurement

- Working with suppliers that have Net Zero goals in place
- Include hardware experts in procurement process to assess life cycle of equipment and embodied carbon

For user devices,
embodied emissions will
often outweigh the
emissions during use